

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15284963

Subordinate Mentorship Of Principals In Public Secondary School Administration In Ebonyi State

Dr. Okoro Mkpuma¹ & Osoego Beatrice (Ph.D Student)²

**¹Primary Education Department (PED),
Ebonyi State College of Education, Ikwo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria**

**¹Lecturer, Department of Educational Foundations (Educational Administration and Planning),
Ebonyi State University Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The study assessed the subordinate mentorship of principals in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. The design of the study was descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised five thousand, nine hundred and thirty-nine (5939) teachers from two hundred and twenty-six (226) public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. The sample of the study comprised three hundred and seventy five (375) teachers from 182 public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Yaro Yamane sampling formula was used to determine the sample size of 375 teachers because the population is finite while proportionate, simple random and stratified sampling techniques were used for sample distribution. The instrument for data collection was a structured Questionnaire titled “Subordinate Mentorship of Principals in Secondary School Administration Questionnaire” (SMPSSAQ). The instrument was face validated by three (3) experts and reliability established with the overall index of 0.65. Out of the 375 administered questionnaire, only 372 were filled completely and returned. Hence, three questionnaire was lost at the end of exercise. The returned 372 questionnaire was used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data collected with regards to research questions while t-test of independent sample was used to test the null hypotheses developed for the study at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that principals’ expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in Ebonyi State public secondary schools to very high extent, but foster friendliness among their subordinates in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State to very low extent. The study further revealed that there was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the mean ratings of rural and urban school teachers on the extent principals expose their subordinates to instructional leadership, but significant difference exist between urban and rural principals on the extent they foster friendliness among their subordinates in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State. One of the implications of the findings is that if school principals do not expose their subordinate to instructional leadership, teachers would be lazy, develop laissez faire attitude towards instruction. Recommendations and suggestions for further studies were also made therein.

Keywords: Principals, Subordinate, mentorship, Subordinate Mentorship, Secondary School Administration

INTRODUCTION

The value of mentorship in every human organization cannot be underestimated. It is imperative to note that the rapid changes and developments in the 21st century require innovation and change in education as well. It is believed that support for subordinates in form of mentoring from school administrators, which provides for innovation and change in schools, not only increases teachers' performance in education, but also can have a positive impact on their job satisfaction. According to Evers and Eacott (2016), the administrators' support refers to act of meeting the needs of staff to increase their performance levels. It include caring, provision of teaching and learning materials, ensuring conducive working environment and training of staff on innovations. These supportive activities would make subordinates feel that they are valuable assets, which in turns may increase the quality of work life and the positive relationship between administrators and subordinates. Perceived administrative support is the subordinates' belief about being cared for and valued for their contributions to the organization by their administrators (Pohl & Galletta, 2016). The attitudes and behaviours that constitute administrators' support consist of the ability of principals to mentor the new subordinates to achieve the stipulated goals of the organization. According to Nwakpa (2016), one of such support services required of principals is to ensure the mentoring or coaching of subordinates to achieve the objectives of teaching and learning in secondary schools.

Mentorship is a process of establishing a learning relationship between people of different experience, or knowledge background. According to Udom, Okoedion and Okolie (2020), mentorship is a relationship in which the more experienced, knowledgeable and trusted person helps to guide a less experienced or less knowledgeable person and the process involved is referred to as mentoring. Mentoring is a learning relationship which is broader than that involved in coaching. The latter is skilled or competency focused, whereas the former is concerned with passing on knowledge, insight and attitudes as well as skills to less experienced person (Agbonifoh & Idubor, 2016). Sawiuk, Taylor and Groom (2017) added that mentorship is most often described as a guiding relationship in which a more experienced person, the mentor, assumes a supportive role by overseeing and encouraging reflection and learning with a less experienced person, the mentee. Peretomode and Ikoya (2019) defined mentorship as "a learning and development partnership between someone with vast or in-depth experience and knowledge (the mentor) and someone who wants to learn, build skills and knowledge while attaining his goals. This implied that mentor is a senior person in respect to maturity and experience providing information, advice, and emotional support for a junior individual in a long-term relationship distinguished by strong emotional commitment on both parties (Kram, 2018). Roa (2015) added that mentoring is a method of teaching and learning, one-to-one, reciprocal career development connection between two individuals who are different in age, temperament, cycle of life, social standing, and/or qualifications. This shows that for mentorship to take place there must be people of different backgrounds of knowledge or experience. One must be less experienced while the other will be more experienced. In the context of this study, mentoring entails the principals having a genuine interest in ensuring that a new teacher and non-tutorial staff (subordinates) develops the talent, skills, expertise, and knowledge required to thrive and add to the success of public secondary schools. Therefore, in this study, the ultimate purpose of mentorship is to ensure that the right ways of doing things are passed on to the subordinates by the principals.

Subordinates mentorship therefore is the systematic way of giving assistance, coaching, supports and caring for staff by the principals to ensure effective and efficient work done in secondary schools. According to Olu-Ajayi (2016), subordinate mentoring is a supportive relationship established between the leader (principal) and the followers (teachers and non-tutorials) where knowledge, skills and experience are shared. In secondary schools, subordinate mentorship is a form of an interaction between the principals and teachers that facilitates the process of cognition, and help teachers to achieve more than each of them could achieve alone. Therefore, for principals of secondary schools to fulfil this mentoring role to their subordinates (teachers) in this study, they have to create conditions which promote the growth and development of these subordinates within their schools. Principals can do this by exposing the

subordinates to instructional leadership, mentor staff on how to foster friendliness, keeping good school community-relationship, ensures career development of staff, mentor subordinates on school discipline, and mentor staff on the innovative methods of teaching.

Instructional leadership is the action that a principal takes, or delegates to others, to promote growth in student learning. According to Onyali and Akinfolarin (2017), instructional leadership involves directing the teachers on time management and supervising them to promote quality of teaching and learning outcomes and enhance the attainment of the educational goals and objectives. Harris, Jones Adams and Cheah (2019) noted that principals as instructional leaders are deeply engaged in the process of teaching and learning. This can make principals the primary ingredient of instructional leadership in effective secondary schools. In this direction, effective changes in classrooms can be regarded as the manifestation of principals' instructional leadership. Ahmed (2016) highlighted instructional leadership of principals to include: designing school goals, communicating school goals, supervision and evaluation of instruction, coordination of the curriculum, monitoring of students' progress, protection of instructional time, maintaining high visibility, providing incentives for teachers, promotion of professional development and providing incentives for students. Harris, Jones, Adams and Cheah (2019) added that the instructional leadership of principals are directly linked to creating the conditions for optimal teaching and learning in schools. In the context of this study, mentoring in instructional leadership involves the administrative activities and roles that are geared towards providing support for teachers and other staff of secondary schools to ensure quality instructional delivery for school effectiveness. The state of art is that most principals do not care about the qualities required of every staff to ensure effective teaching and learning in schools (Nwakpa, 2016). This situation can mar the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Through instructional leadership mentorship, every members of the schools tends to understand his/her roles. This situation would reduce tension and promote friendliness among staff and students.

School friendliness is another important factor in maintaining effective school administration. Friendliness in school involves the ability of principals to train the staff on how to maintain good rapport and conducive atmosphere between members of the school community for effective teaching and learning to take place (Ukpong, 2020). According to Sinem, Ramazan and Ahmet (2021), mentoring teachers for friendliness has to do with principals relating with teachers to work together for mutual support. In addition, the manner in which teachers and other staff of the school worked together as a group can significantly influence students' outcomes in schools. Staff in schools need to be mentored on how to work together for healthy social environments and as well substantiate the need for relationship development in their school environment. The principals must be able to train teachers to develop the quality of behaving in a pleasant, kind way towards one another. According to Abari, Ibikunle, Animashaun and Oguntuga (2016), positive behaviours of staff in schools could help to sustain teachers and add value to their activities. Millie and Anne (2018) also added that friendships in school help teachers and students develop emotionally and morally. Friendliness is one of the most important of all the relational components in school administration. It is therefore, essential that school principals mentor teachers to develop the trust factor necessary for them to follow and support their efforts. The building and sustaining friendliness with teachers via communicative and supportive behaviours is the overarching trust-promoting behaviour of the principal. In this study, the principal creating atmosphere of friendliness through their mentoring can foster the overall development of teachers. This is because the teachers will always lean on principals for vital information needed for effective change in teaching and learning. Apart from maintaining school mentoring for school friendliness, principals can also mentor subordinates to develop positive school community-relationship. However, principals' ability in mentoring the subordinates in the area of discipline of behaviour can equally vary depending on school location.

School location is a variable that may affect the subordinate mentorship of principals. School location refers to the particular place, in relation to other areas in the physical environment (rural or urban), where the school is sited (Ekaette, Ameh and Owan, 2020). According to Arop, Ekpang and Owan (2018), rural

life is uniform, homogeneous and less complex than that of urban area, with cultural diversity which is often suspected to affect students' academic achievement. This is because urban schools are better favoured with respect to distribution of social amenities such as pipe bone water, electricity, healthcare facilities, while the rural schools are less favoured (Owan, Duruamakudim, Ekpe, Owan & Agurokpon, 2019). This is also true in the distribution of educational facilities and teachers. These prevailing conditions imply that learning opportunities in Nigerian schools differ from school to school. It would appear therefore that students in Nigerian urban schools have more educational opportunities than their counterparts in rural schools. Such opportunities could be social comforts, such as pipe bone water, power, medical services, offices, good roads among others (Ntibi & Edoho, 2017). Therefore, school location is the physical attributes of schools as a result of being in urban or rural areas.

It is important to note that schools in rural areas may face some unique challenges. It also may be noticeable that the vast physical distances existing between one school district and another along with small school sizes that dictate a smaller teaching staff can impact the effectiveness of mentoring programmes. However, there are ways to overcome these difficulties. One method is online coaching and e-mentoring. In rural schools in Nigeria, online mentoring programmes might seem to fill an important needs (Arop, Ekpang & Owan, 2018). Nevertheless, opportunities like electricity and network services seem not to be steadily available in rural areas as opposed to urban areas. This situation might significantly affect principals' ability to initiate and implement subordinate mentorship needed for positive transformation in teaching and learning. This study was therefore designed to determine the subordinate mentorship in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the values underpinning mentoring in school administration such as increasing satisfaction and retention rate to members of school organisation, increasing self-confidence, developing competence, encouraging collaboration and competition among members of an organization, public secondary school principals in Ebonyi State seem to have ignored mentoring in school administration. There is perceived inability of principals in Ebonyi State to expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in Ebonyi State needed for effective school administration. It is important to note that exposing teachers and other staff of the schools would help them to understand their role in bringing desirable changes in the life of students. In addition, the researcher wonders if principals' mentor subordinates on how to foster friendliness, and keeping good school-community relationship necessary for administrative effectiveness in schools. More so, there are innovations in the area of teaching and administration of school system, the principals must initiate and support career development of teachers in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. It could be possible that most principals do not care about the staff development, and this situation affect the subordinate ability to participate actively in performing teaching and administrative tasks. Finally, maintaining school discipline in school is becoming challenging and cumbersome in modern times, where most of the traditional values have been depreciated by western culture.

The principals therefore need to mentor the subordinates to take active measures in maintaining school discipline in school administration. The problem that this study seeks to address is of two folds: first, indiscipline, poor academic performance among teachers and students, all as a result of poor school administration of school principals. This study sought to see the extent the school administrators mentor their subordinates in order to achieve the goals and objectives of secondary education in Ebonyi State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to assess the subordinate mentorship of principals in public secondary school administration in Ebonyi State. Specifically, the study was designed to determine the;

1. extent to which principals expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in the administration of Ebonyi State public secondary schools.
2. extent to which principals foster friendliness in their subordinates in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent do principals expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in the administration of Ebonyi State public secondary schools?
2. To what extent do principals foster friendliness among their subordinates in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State?

Hypotheses

The following two (2) null hypotheses were formulated for the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural teachers on the extent principals expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural teachers on the extent principals foster friendliness among their subordinates in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The literature review was discussed based on the following sub-headings:

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study is presented on the schematic diagram below:

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the subordinate mentorship of principals in secondary school administration in Ebonyi State (Source: Researcher’s Self-Made, 2025).

The schematic representation above shows that effective secondary school administration (dependent variable) is depended on principals’ ability to initiate subordinate mentorship (independent variable) in the area of instructional leadership and staff friendliness. The subordinate mentorship of secondary school principals may vary depending on the condition of school location (Intervening Variable). In addition, the mentorship and administration of secondary schools might also vary depending on the differences that

exist in location of schools in terms of urban and rural secondary schools (Intervening variable 1). Below are the review and the explanation of these variables.

School Subordinates

Schools, like many other organizations, tend to follow standard organizational structures. Secondary school system has a definite hierarchy and clear boundaries as to which employees or departments are responsible for various tasks involved in school operation. Like businesses and nonprofit organizations, the organizational structure of a school outlines who reports to whom and who is responsible for what. Schools typically have administrators (principals) who are responsible for whole-school operations and supervision. According to Arop (2018), principals are subordinate to the secondary education authority, who they report to directly. Principals often have one or several vice-principals assisting them with their duties. The author further states that there are teachers of different subjects divided into teams based on grade levels or academic subject areas, and non-tutorial staff or office workers and support staff to carry out various administrative functions necessary for school operations. These staff that operate within the framework of secondary schools is referred to as school subordinates. Ahmed (2016) maintains that subordinates are school personnel that report directly to principals within the organizational structure of the schools. These include the vice-principals, deans of studies, bursar, librarian, counselors, and teachers of various subject specialisations among others.

The principals as the head of secondary school must always take care of these subordinates in order to attain the educational objectives. However, in this study, school subordinates refer to teachers that carryout teaching and learning activities of the schools.

Subordinate Mentorship

Mentoring is a progressive and non-competitive process that fosters pride, fulfillment, acceptance, and continuity in the protégé while promoting independence, autonomy, and identity in the mentor. Mentoring is an explicit and implicit interaction between two individuals - a senior mentor and a junior protégé (Little, 2017). Ever since late 1970s, there has been much discussion about the worth of persons in mentoring relationships, with the emphasis on the mentoring relationship's quality (Higgins & Kram, 2018). Eby (2019) emphasized this point, describing mentorship as "an intense growth partnership. According to Ekechukwu and Horsfall (2015), the purpose of mentoring in Secondary school is to promote academics' professional development throughout their careers and to encourage brilliance in teaching and learning, research, and academic leadership. Peretomode (2017) stated mentorship is more than offering instructions on how to work more successfully or deal with a specific difficulty. It entails the mentor having a genuine interest in ensuring that a mentee develops the talent, skills, expertise, and knowledge required to thrive and add to the organization's success.

In secondary schools, mentorship is very important in ensuring effective school administrations. According to Undiyaundeye and Basake (2017), the pursuit of development by new teachers in Nigeria is not without challenges, fears and anxieties and therefore mentoring can be an effective way of mitigating the stress of new teachers, help them resolve challenges and help them achieve their career goals more readily. Kram (2018) maintained that mentoring is a means of transferring the skills which protégés need and can apply in diverse professional circumstances, promote learning and productive use of knowledge, definition of goals and career paths and job satisfaction. Ayodeji and Adebayo (2015) also indicated that mentoring can ensure and maintain effective school administration in Nigeria, because teaching is a multifaceted and complex task that demands the guidance and experience of senior academic staff. Undiyaundeye and Basake (2017) also stated that mentoring is needed in schools because it increases job satisfaction, self-confidence, enhances staff retention rate, encourages professional growth, develops competence and encourages collaboration while reducing competition. This view is also corroborated by Nnaji, Uko and Nwafor (2015) who stated that professional competence of newly employed staff could be significantly enhanced through mentoring. Sola (2018) also concur with this view that mentoring has a significant influence on the career development of academic staff. Kolade (2015) advocated mentoring as a means of building a new generation of academics and responsible leadership. Omale, Oguche, Duru and

Idodo (2017) averred that mentoring improves staff retention and knowledge transfer in schools. The above scholarly views show that mentorship is essential for school administration.

Therefore, the present study will determine the principals' subordinates' mentorship in secondary school administration in Ebonyi state. The study looked into the extent principals establish staff friendliness, instructional leadership, establish school-community relationship, maintain school discipline and initiate career development of staff through partnership support and communication.

Instructional leadership

In school administration, the principals have a lot of roles to play in mentoring teachers especially in the area of instructional purposes. The principals have to be leader of instruction. Instructional leadership means motivating teachers to teach and create a safe teaching-learning condition in the schools. According to Uddin (2020), instructional leadership is a process of directing and motivating teachers a team in teaching and learning in order to attain objectives. As an effective instructional leader, the principal in the school, hire, support, and retain good teachers while developing or removing the less effective ones for successful classroom instruction. According to Edmonton Public Schools (2018), instructional leadership involves principals becoming leading-learners who successfully collaborate with other school leaders and nurture a learning community that supports and improves students' achievement. This implies that the principals must cordially work with every personnel in school to bring about effective change in the life of students.

The role of the principal in instructional leadership is critical for a school. This leadership role in the school is neither new nor straightforward. This instructional leadership is evolving day by day, and it is not confined to the principal only. Other school subordinates like vice-principals can also exhibit such instructional roles. A school leader's instructional leadership can be compared to the captain of a ship who leads the crews and passengers to the right destination. Therefore, this study aims to explore the role of the principal in directing and guiding teachers to attain the instructional objectives as part of mentoring in school administration in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Staff Friendliness

Friendship is a relationship between two people in which each participant values the other and successfully communicates this fact to the other. According to Uri (2020), friendship is the relationship between two parties that are equal or unequal which is based on trust, happiness, solidarity and fairness. In this relationship, each person values one another. It is essential to note that if staff is aware that the principal values them, it will have a pronounced impact on staff own self-valuation. Therefore, friendliness is the process by which principals in their subordinate mentorship foster positive relationship with the staff that is based on trust, happiness, problem-solving and educating among others. Fostering friendliness of school principals with subordinates are necessary to induce trust and support from them for any policy being formulated in the school system. This means that the task of the school principals is to formulate the goals to be attained, provide the required resources and direct the activities of the school through the engagement of teachers, non-tutorials and students to realise such goals (Rajendran, 2017).

School principals must always endeavour to generate good working climate by encouraging friendliness through interactions with subordinates, being sensitive to human factors and needs yet not oblivious of the objectives of the school and encouraging shared responsibility which would foster the exchange of ideas among staff of the school. These are achievable when there is a rational decision-making process in the school. It will enlist co-operation among staff and reduce complaints, allegations and disobedience against school managers (Maicibi, 2016). The single factor common to every change initiative is the development and improvement of relationships. If relationships improve, things may get better. If they remain the same or get worse, trust and confidence is lost and such action may hinder the attainment of schools' objectives. Thus, educational managers are expected to be relationship builders in diverse ways with both teachers and students. The most successful teachers are the ones who are inspired by a cordial relationship being developed with the principals through motivation to put in their best while discharging their official responsibilities (Nleremchi, 2018). This is the reason why Rajendran (2017) posted that it is

important to note that a school principals does not work in isolation in a school. The kind of friendliness that is established between the school principals and staff may determine the kind of collaboration that is practiced and how the school goal could be attained (Udoka, 2019). Therefore, friendliness helps principal and staff to share their experiences together in solving the problem of the school.

In the context of this study, friendliness deals with involvement of teachers and other staff in decision making of the teachers, attaining to the needs of the teachers and correcting them constructively and judiciously in order to feel at home with the school environment. This situation will invariably help the principals to mentor the subordinates positively to attain the objective of secondary education in Nigeria. However, it seems that poor friendly relationships between school principals and their staff may affect their job performance. Therefore, there is need to find out the extent principals' mentorship foster friendliness in their subordinates in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of the study is anchored on Human Relation Theory

Human Relations Theory

The human relations theory was propounded by Mary Packer Follet in 1933. Human Relations Theory states that in addition to finding the best technological strategies to improve output, it was beneficial for administrators to consider the human elements in the organization. The theory was concerned with the human problems encountered in organizations such as welfare, motivation, retirement benefits among others and therefore concluded that such problems can only be minimized when there is co-operation among workers. Based on this, she developed four organizational principles, all of which centre on co-ordination: coordination by direct contact with the people concerned, coordination in the early stages, coordination as the reciprocal relation of all the factors in a situation, and coordination as a continuing process. The human relations theory has its central idea that the human factor is very important in the achievement of organizational goals. The proponent of this theory holds the view that workers will achieve better if their personal welfare was taken into consideration.

Human relations theory is relevant to the present study because it buttresses the fact that the administrative arm of any organization especially the school should consider the welfare of the employees as utmost importance. Therefore, for proper administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State, the principals must mentor their subordinates to take full advantage in the growth and development of the system.

Review of Empirical Studies

Harriet, Kinikonda and Jacklyne (2022) carried out a study to establish the mentorship roles of head-teachers as school cultural builders influence the performance of the newly deployed/transferred teachers in Lufwanyama District of Zambia. The study was anchored on Kram's Mentor Role Theory and Path-Goal Theory. A mixed methods research approach and a descriptive survey design were adopted. The target population of the study was teachers 112 , head-teachers and 311 Heads of Departments. Purposive sampling was used to select 16 public secondary schools and 16 head-teachers. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were adopted to select 33 out of 112 Heads of Departments (HODs) and 93 teachers. Questionnaire were used to collect data from teachers and HODs, while interviews were used to collect data from head-teachers. Quantitative data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 and presented in frequencies, tables and percentages. Qualitative data were categorized into various themes and reported in form of narratives and direct quotations. The findings revealed that the mentorship roles of head-teachers were important in determining the performance of newly deployed/transferred teachers. However, it was established that most of the head-teachers do not adequately coach newly deployed/transferred teachers and do not effectively supervise and examine teachers' lesson notes in order to build their professional abilities.

This study relates with the present study as it covered the extent of instructional leadership secondary schools in terms of supervision of instruction which is one of the major variables of the present study. However, the study differs from the present study in area of the study and population because it used head-teachers while the present study will use principals. The study also did not cover other variables under investigation such as friendliness, school discipline and career development of teachers which the present study is stipulated to cover.

Ikenga and Ogbaga (2021) investigated the Influence of Working Relationship between Principals and Teachers on Students Activities in Secondary Schools in Awgu Education Zone of Enugu State. The main purpose of the study was to determine how principals ensuring friendliness with teachers enhanced students' activities. Three research questions guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 54 principals and 785 teachers in the public secondary schools in the zone. Purposive sampling technique was employed to draw 28 principals and 252 teachers from 28 non-proportionately selected schools in the zone. A structured questionnaire in three clusters (A-C) containing 25 items titled Principal and Teachers Working Relationship on Students Academic Performance Questionnaire (PTWRSAPQ) was used for data collection. Three experts in Administration and Planning, Department of Educational Foundations and 2 experts from Measurement and Evaluation Unit, Department of Science Education both from Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki validated the instrument. Cronbach alpha was used to test the reliability of the instrument and the whole 25 items returned a coefficient of 0.61. Data collected were analyzed using mean (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (SD) to answer the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that the mean responses of principals and teachers on the influence of their working relationship on students' performance in classroom activities was no significant, the mean responses of principals and teachers based on location on the influence of their working relationship on students' performance in external examinations was not significantly different, and the mean responses of the principals and teachers based on gender on the influence of their working relationship on students' performance in internal examinations was not significantly different.

This study relates with the present study as it covered the extent to which principals' mentorship foster friendliness in their subordinates in secondary schools in terms of establishing positive working relationship with staff. The study also relates with the present study in design, method of data collection and analysis. However, the study differs from the present study in area of the study. The study also did not cover other variables under investigation such as school discipline, career development and demographic variables that influences principals' ability in school mentorship; hence, the need for the present study.

Oguejiofor, Igbokwe and Amaeze (2022) investigated the relationship between management of principals' social relationship skills and effective school organization in public secondary school in Enugu State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were answered and tested. The study adopted a correlation research with a population of 295 principals from 295 public secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. The sample size of the study is 236 principals representing 80% of the population drawn from 236 schools. The simple random sampling technique was used to arrive at the sample. Two instruments titled Management of Principals' Social Skills Scale (MPSSS) and Effective School Organization Scale (ESOS) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated using confirmatory factor analysis. Internal consistency reliability coefficients of 0.76 and 0.71 were computed for MPSSS and ESOS respectively through Cronbach alpha. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that principals' conflict resolution and interpersonal skills management are significant predictors of effective school administration. The study also revealed that creating friendliness among the staff of secondary schools helps in the effective administration of secondary schools.

This study relates with the present study as it covered the extent to which principals' mentorship foster friendliness in secondary school administration in terms of establishing positive working relationship with staff. However, the study differs from the present study in area of the study, design and method of data collection and analysis. The study also did not cover other variables under investigation such as school discipline, career development and demographic variables that influence principals' ability in school mentorship. This underscores the need for the present study.

METHODOLOGY

The design of this study was a descriptive survey type. A descriptive survey design is mainly concerned with documenting, describing and explaining events as they are, without any manipulation of what is observed. According to Abonyi, Okereke, Omebe, Anugwo, and Nnachi (2022), descriptive survey design is the type that systematically and accurately describes a population, situation, or phenomenon without the manipulation of any variable but only observes and measures them to get the outcome. The descriptive design was considered appropriate for this study because it is versatile and practical and it permits the collection of original data from the respondents to investigate the subordinate mentorship of principals in both urban and rural secondary school administration in Ebonyi State. The population of the study comprised five thousand, nine hundred and thirty-nine (5939) teachers from two hundred and twenty-six (226) public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. The sample of the study comprised three hundred and seventy five (375) teachers from 182 public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Yaro Yamane sampling formula was used to determine the sample size of 375 teachers because the population is finite while proportionate, simple random and stratified sampling techniques were used for sample distribution. The instrument for data collection was a structured Questionnaire titled “Subordinate Mentorship of Principals in Secondary School Administration Questionnaire” (SMPSSAQ). The instrument was face validated by three (3) experts and reliability established with the overall index of 0.65. Out of the 375 administered questionnaire, only 372 were filled completely and returned. Hence, three questionnaire was lost at the end of exercise. The returned 372 questionnaire was used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data collected with regards to research questions while t-test of independent sample was used to test the null hypotheses developed for the study at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The results of the study were presented in tables on the three research questions and hypotheses.

4.1 Research Question 1: *To what extent do principals’ expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in Ebonyi State public secondary schools?*

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Teachers on the extent principals expose their Subordinates to Instructional Leadership in Ebonyi State Public Secondary Schools

S/N	Items Statements	N	Sum	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Allowing teachers make input on matters relating to teaching strategy	372	1144	3.08	0.87	VHE
2	Encouraging teachers to use available teaching facilities	372	1134	3.05	0.82	VHE
3	Supporting appraisal of new teachers	372	1108	2.98	0.82	HA
4	Assisting teachers with ideas that will help them prepare good lesson notes	372	1138	3.06	0.79	VHE
5	Guiding teachers in the development of instructional activities	372	1130	3.04	0.79	VHE
6	Guiding teachers in evaluating students on innovative assessment techniques	372	1082	2.91	0.76	HE
7	Assisting teachers in designing programme of counseling in learning process	372	1160	3.12	0.86	VHE
8	Guiding teachers on better ways of approaching students’ learning in classroom	372	1130	3.04	0.79	VHE
Overall Mean & Standard Deviation Scores				3.04	0.81	VHE

Key: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE)

The Data in **Table I** show that Item 1-8 had mean scores ranging from 3.08, 3.05, 2.98, 3.06, 3.04, 2.91, 3.12, and 3.04 with their standard deviation scores ranging from 0.87, 0.82, 0.82, 0.79, 0.79, 0.76, 0.86, and 0.79 respectively which are above the criterion mean value of 2.50. The grand mean score of 3.04 and standard deviation of 0.81 is an indication that principals to large extent allow teachers make input on matters relating to teaching strategy, encourage teachers to use available teaching facilities, support appraisal of new teachers, assist teachers with ideas that will help them prepare good lesson notes, guide teachers in the development of instructional activities, guide teachers in evaluating students on innovative assessment techniques, assist teachers in designing programme of counseling in learning process, and guide teachers on better ways of approaching students' learning in classroom. This implies that principals' expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in Ebonyi State public secondary schools to very high extent.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do principals foster friendliness among their subordinates in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State?*

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Teachers on the extent Principals Foster Friendliness among their Subordinates in Public Secondary Schools in Ebonyi State

S/N	Items Statements	N	Sum	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
9	Appreciates subordinates for excellent performance	372	731	1.97	0.80	LE
10	Ensuring that every staff attend staff meeting to encourage togetherness.	372	821	2.21	0.79	LE
11	Developing relationship by allowing staff in planning special occasion like end of the year party	372	814	2.19	0.75	LE
12	Supporting teachers to attend staff welfare ceremonies so as to build relationship	372	782	2.10	0.76	LE
13	Establishing a friendly atmosphere to enable subordinates do their work well	372	762	2.05	0.79	LE
14	Allowing staff participate in decision making process	372	801	2.15	0.79	LE
15	Delegating roles to all staff to ensure sense of belongings in administration of the school	372	754	2.03	0.74	LE
16	Ensuring that some of the needs of staff are attained to encourage their loyalty in doing their job	372	778	2.09	0.82	LE
Overall Mean & Standard Deviation Scores				2.10	0.78	LE

Key: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE)

The Data in Table 2 show that Item 9-16 had mean scores ranging from 1.97, 2.21, 2.19, 2.10, 2.05, 2.15, 2.03, and 2.09 with their standard deviation scores ranging from 0.80, 0.79, 0.75, 0.76, 0.79, 0.79, 0.74, and 0.82 respectively which are above the criterion mean value of 2.50. The grand mean score of 2.10 and standard deviation of 0.78 is an indication that principals appreciates subordinates for excellent performance, ensuring that every staff attend staff meeting to encourage togetherness, develop relationship by allowing staff in planning special occasion like end of the year party, support teachers to attend staff welfare ceremonies so as to build relationship, establish a friendly atmosphere to enable subordinates do their work well, allow staff participate in decision making process, delegate roles to all staff to ensure sense of belongings in administration of the school, and ensures that some of the needs of staff are attained to encourage their loyalty in doing their job. Hence, principals foster friendliness among their subordinates in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State to very low extent.

Test of hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural teachers on the extent principals expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State. This was analysed in Table 3 below:

Table 3: t-test Summary of Rural and Urban School Teachers on the extent Principals expose their Subordinates to Instructional Leadership in the Administration of Secondary Schools in Ebonyi State

S/N	Variables	NO	\bar{X}	S.D	Df	t	P-Value	Decision
1	Rural	180	3.01	.92	370	-1.51	.133	NS
	Urban	192	3.14	.81				
2	Rural	180	3.14	.86	370	2.06	.040	S
	Urban	192	2.96	.78				
3	Rural	180	3.07	.87	370	2.01	.46	NS
	Urban	192	2.89	.77				
4	Rural	180	3.06	.79	370	0.05	.96	NS
	Urban	192	3.06	.81				
5	Rural	180	3.13	.86	370	2.28	.023	S
	Urban	192	2.95	.71				
6	Rural	180	3.09	.76	370	4.52	.00	S
	Urban	192	2.74	.73				
7	Rural	180	3.04	.89	370	-1.61	.108	NS
	Urban	192	3.19	.82				
8	Rural	180	2.99	.80	370	-1.14	.254	NS
	Urban	192	3.09	.79				
Grand Mean			3.02	0.78	370	0.83	0.25	NS

Key: Significant (S), Not Significant (NS)

Data in **Table 3** show that the responses of rural and urban school teachers had significant difference in item 2, 5 and 6, and no significant difference in items 1, 3, 4, 7 and 8 respectively. It also showed overall t-calculated value of 0.83 and P-value of 0.25 which is greater than the chosen level of significance, 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural teachers on the extent principals expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State was upheld.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural teachers on the extent principals foster friendliness among their subordinates in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

This was analysed in Table 7 below:

Table 4: t-test Summary of Rural and Urban School Teachers on the extent Principals Fosters Friendliness among their Subordinates to Instructional Leadership in the Administration of Secondary Schools in Ebonyi State

S/N	Variables	NO	\bar{X}	S.D	Df	t	P-Value	Decision
	Rural	180	2.22	0.90				
9	Urban	192	3.14	0.81	370	-10.39	.00	S
	Rural	180	2.39	0.91				
10	Urban	192	2.96	0.78	370	-6.49	.00	S
	Rural	180	2.32	0.84				
11	Urban	192	2.89	0.77	370	-6.77	.00	S
	Rural	180	2.28	0.83				
12	Urban	192	3.06	0.81	370	-9.17	.00	S
	Rural	180	2.16	0.91				
13	Urban	192	2.95	0.71	370	-9.38	.00	S
	Rural	180	2.33	0.88				
14	Urban	192	2.74	0.73	370	-4.83	.00	S
	Rural	180	2.25	0.88				
15	Urban	192	3.19	0.82	370	-10.64	.00	S
	Rural	180	2.26	0.85				
16	Urban	192	3.08	0.79	370	-9.69	.00	S
	Grand Mean		2.70	0.81	370	-8.42	0.00	S

Key: Significant (S), Not Significant (NS)

Data in **Table 4** show that the responses of rural and urban school teachers had significant difference in items 9-16 respectively. It also showed overall t-calculated value of 0.83 and P-value of 0.00 which is less than the chosen level of significance, 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural teachers on the extent principals foster friendliness among their subordinates in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State was not upheld. Hence, there is significant difference between urban and rural principals on the extent they foster friendliness among their subordinates in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

DISCUSSION

The study explored the subordinate mentorship of principals in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. The finding of the study revealed that principals' expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in Ebonyi State public secondary schools to very high extent. This findings corroborates with the findings of Bada, Tengku, Ariffin and Nordin (2020) that instructional leadership of principals can help subordinates in secondary schools to develop and improve their professional knowledge, skills, and abilities in handling teaching and learning difficulties. The finding was also supported by the findings of Hafsat, Tengku and Hasniza (2020) that there was positive perception of teachers on the instructional leadership of principals in terms of defining school mission; managing instructional programs; and developing a positive school learning climate, are significantly and positively associated with teachers' effectiveness. However, the inability of principals to adopt instructional leadership in the administration of secondary schools can hinder the attainment of teaching and learning objectives. The obvious implication of this finding is that principals are expected to know the strengths and weaknesses of subordinates and show genuine concern for their health, welfare and professional

growth. Similarly, the principal, as an instructional resource, must be able to identify good teachers and provide feedback that promotes professional growth. Agusiobo and Etukokwu (2017) added that the principal, as communicator, must communicate to the subordinate that all children can learn and experience success, and learner outcomes must be clearly defined to guide instructional programs. For visibility, the principal must model behavior, informally drop in on classrooms and make staff development activities a priority.

The goals of principals relate to the ability of the principal to engage staff in order to make sure that the school has a clear mission, which is the students' academic performance. No wonder Al-Mahdy, Emam and Hallinger (2018) submitted that the principal has the responsibility of communicating and articulating the vision of learning and building support because the attainment of the school's mission cannot be achieved solely by the principal, but by communicating with other stakeholders in the school community. Managing the instructional program in this dimension, the principal has the sole responsibility of ensuring that the subordinates (teachers) provide good quality teaching and learning in the school in order to achieve educational goals. The result of the null hypothesis I revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of rural and urban school teachers on the extent principals expose their subordinates to instructional leadership in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State. This implies that teachers view their principals in the same perspective in the aspect of instructional leadership behaviour in urban and rural schools in Ebonyi State. The implication of the findings is that location of schools should not affect the instructional leadership quality of principals if the purpose of administration are to be attained.

The finding of the study also revealed that principals foster friendliness among their subordinates in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State to very low extent. This finding is in tandem with the findings of Ikenga and Ogbaga (2021) who submitted that most principals in secondary schools in Nigeria lacks the leadership quality in terms of fostering friendliness among staff and students in order for them to feel sense of belongings and work collaboratively to achieve the objectives of teaching and learning. Hence, a school environment that is filled with rancor and acrimony, lack of trust and respect to one another's view or opinions can affect the effective administration of secondary schools. Similarly, the finding of the study corroborates with Oguejiofor, Igbokwe and Amaeze (2022) that interpersonal skills management are significant predictors of effective school administration but school principals barely used these skills in school administration. The implication of the finding is that creating friendliness among the subordinates in secondary schools helps teachers and non-tutorial staff to feel at home with one another, and this invariably would enhance administration of secondary schools. This idea was supported by Rajendran (2017) who held that fostering friendliness of school principals with subordinates are necessary to induce trust and support from them for any policy being formulated in the school system.

The result of null hypothesis 2 held that there was significant difference between urban and rural principals on the extent they foster friendliness among their subordinates in the administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State. This implies that the environment of schools can affect the ability of principals fostering friendliness among the subordinates. This finding was not supported Ikenga and Ogbaga (2021) whose findings submitted that there was no significant difference based on the working relationship between principals and staff in school administration. However, it is imperative to note that environment is that most determinant of behaviour irrespective of inherent or achieved potentials. Hence, the behaviour of principals in schools can be shaped by the school environment. Ekaette, Ameh and Owan (2020) added that the poor conditions of rural school environment can make staff to develop poor psychological state like anger, anxiety and frustration. This psychological state can hinder the ability of principals in adopting good relationship measures with the subordinates.

CONCLUSION

The study assessed principals' subordinate mentorship in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. It is imperative to note that principals' subordinate mentorship practice have significant

effect on the administration of secondary schools and for effective implementation of school programmes. The study concluded that the extent to which principals expose their subordinates to instructional leadership and foster friendliness, could help in effective administration of public secondary school in Ebonyi State. In addition, the application of these subordinate mentorship would invariably help principals to manage the school resources effectively and establish working conditions needed for effective change in the life of staff and students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were based on the findings of the study

1. The Secondary Education Board (SEB) in conjunction with the State Ministry of Education should organize a workshop to train principals on the instructional leadership skills required of principals in modern school administration. This would help principals to defining school mission; managing instructional programmes and developing a positive school learning climate due to effective subordinate mentorship.
2. The Guidance and Counselling Units of secondary schools should be used in training principals and subordinates on the aspect of fostering friendliness needed for efficient and effective administration of secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

REFERENCES

- Nleremchi, P. N. (2018). Influence of staff-principal relationships on teacher performance in secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Practice and Research*, 15(2), 76–84.
- Nnaji, A. O., Uko, E. S., & Nwafor, B. U. (2015). Enhancing staff competence through mentoring in public secondary schools. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 18(4), 204–213.
- Nwakpa, P. (2016). *Administrative support and staff performance in secondary schools*. Abakaliki: Ebofem Press.
- Oguejiofor, C. C., Igbokwe, U. L., & Amaeze, F. (2022). Relationship between management of principals' social relationship skills and effective school organization in public secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy Studies*, 14(1), 78–90.
- Olu-Ajayi, O. A. (2016). Subordinate mentoring and leadership success in school management. *Journal of Educational Supervision*, 4(1), 52–61.
- Omale, J. O., Oguche, D., Duru, C., & Idodo, E. (2017). Mentorship and leadership development in schools. *Journal of Educational Leadership in Nigeria*, 6(1), 37–49.
- Onyali, L. C., & Akinfolarin, C. A. (2017). Instructional leadership as a tool for effective teaching in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 3(6), 12–21.
- Owan, V. J., Duruamakudim, C. E., Ekpe, M. B., Owan, J. J., & Agurokpon, E. A. (2019). School location and students' academic performance: A study of rural and urban schools. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 3(5), 185–191.
- Peretomode, V. F. (2017). *Educational administration: Applied concepts and theoretical perspectives*. Lagos: Joja Press.
- Peretomode, V. F., & Ikoya, P. O. (2019). *Educational administration: Applied concepts and theoretical perspectives (3rd ed.)*. Lagos: Joja Educational Research and Publishers.
- Pohl, S., & Galletta, M. (2016). The role of perceived organizational support and supportive supervision in the relationship between job stress and work engagement among university lecturers. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 30(6), 893–909.
- Rajendran, N. (2017). School management and leadership: The role of principal-subordinate relationship. *International Journal of Educational Leadership*, 9(1), 56–69.
- Roa, R. A. (2015). *Mentorship in education: A learning partnership*. New Delhi: Global Education Publishers.

- Sawiuk, R., Taylor, W. G., & Groom, R. (2017). Exploring formalized elite coach mentoring programmes in the UK: 'We've had to play the game'. *Sport, Education and Society*, 22(4), 523–536.
- Sinem, K., Ramazan, A., & Ahmet, C. (2021). Principal mentoring and staff relationships in effective school administration. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 4(2), 35–44.
- Sola, A. (2018). Mentorship as a determinant of professional development in academic institutions. *Journal of Professional Studies*, 7(3), 23–35.
- Uddin, A. S. (2020). Instructional leadership and its effect on school improvement. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 23(2), 99–114.
- Udoka, F. C. (2019). Principals' friendliness and its impact on school staff collaboration. *Contemporary Issues in Education*, 14(1), 40–49.
- Udom, S. U., Okoedion, C., & Okolie, U. C. (2020). *Mentoring and career development in educational settings*. Lagos: Pacific Printers.
- Ukpong, M. (2020). *Friendliness in school administration: The role of principals in fostering staff relations*. Uyo: Lifeline Press.
- Undiyaundeye, F. A., & Basake, J. A. (2017). Mentoring new teachers in Nigerian secondary schools: Challenges and prospects. *Nigerian Journal of Teacher Education and Teaching*, 11(2), 22–36.
- Uri, M. T. (2020). The psychology of workplace friendships and productivity. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 35(2), 189–205